

Supplement Figure 1. Selection of patients. Of 703 patients with mRCC, we selected 496 patients who were treated with VEGFR-TKIs as first-line in this study.



mRCC, metastatic renal cell carcinoma; VEGFR, vascular endothelial growth factor receptor; TKI, tyrosine kinase inhibitor; mammalian target of rapamycin; NIVO, nivolumab; IPI, ipilimumab, IO, immuno-oncology drug